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COMBINING NEURAL CLASSIFIERS IN EMG DIAGNOSIS

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Abstract

In the case of difficult pattern recognition problems, the combination of the outputs of multiple classifiers using for input multiple feature sets, can improve the overall classification performance. In this work a modular neural network decision support system was developed for the assessment of the electromyographic (EMG) signal recorded from normal subjects and subjects suffering with myopathy and motor neuron disease. Six different feature sets were computed from the motor unit action potentials (MUAPs) composing the EMG signal, as follows: (i) time domain parameters, (ii) frequency domain parameters, (iii) cepstral coefficients and (iv) three different wavelet coefficients (Daubechies, Chui, and Battle-Lemarie). The multiple feature sets were inputted into multiple self-organising feature map (SOFM) classifiers and the classification results were combined using majority voting. Furthermore, a confidence measure was computed which weighted the contribution of each feature set to the final diagnostic yield. The average diagnostic yield for the individual feature sets was 69.1% whereas when combining the six classification results was 76.9%. The use of the confidence measure enhanced further the diagnostic yield to 79.6%.

1 Introduction

The development of decision support systems based on artificial neural networks (ANN) has shown promising results in different areas of medical applications [1]. ANN are very well suited for the analysis of biomedical data because of their properties to be fault tolerant concerning incomplete or degraded data, to generalize over unknown input patterns, and to adapt and learn complex nonlinear relationships. In addition to these characteristics, neural networks can combine data of a different nature in one system, such as data derived from clinical protocols and laboratory data obtained from measurements and features from signals and images, thus forming an integrated diagnostic system [2]. The combination of multiple classification results obtained by multiple classifiers and/or feature sets can improve the overall classification performance. Furthermore, the use of a confidence measure by weighting the individual classification results before combining, can further improve the overall performance. The objective of this study was to investigate the usefulness of combining neural network classifiers in the development of a decision support system for neuromuscular disorders based on electromyographic (EMG) findings.

The diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders is a naturally complex and difficult problem to investigate. This group of disorders affects the brain and spinal cord, nerves, or muscles. The main characteristic of this group of disorders is muscular weakness and/or wasting, with the life expectancy of many sufferers being considerably reduced. Early detection and diagnosis of these diseases by laboratory tests and neurophysiological examinations, like EMG are essential for their prognosis, management, and prevention. The shapes of motor unit action potentials (MUAPs) composing the EMG signal, provide an important source of information for the assessment of neuromuscular disorders.

The objective of this study was to design, develop, and test a decision support system which mimics the decision making process carried out by the expert neurophysiologist in MUAP analysis where the statistics of MUAP features are compared to normal reference values [3]. The statistics for each subject of multiple features extracted from the MUAP waveforms were fed into multiple SOFM classifiers, and the classification results were combined in order to improve the diagnostic yield. The feature sets extracted, were: (i) the time domain parameters, (ii) the frequency domain parameters, (iii) the cepstral coefficients and (iv) the wavelet transform coefficients. Beyond the classification result, the classifiers yielded a confidence measure which decided the contribution of each feature set to the final diagnostic yield. It was shown that the diagnostic yield achieved when combining the classification results exceeded the average diagnostic yield for the individual feature sets. The use of the confidence measure enhanced further the diagnostic yield. Also the variance of the final diagnostic yield was significantly reduced.

2 Material

In this study, EMG was recorded from the biceps brachii muscle at a slight voluntary contraction for 5 seconds using the concentric needle electrode. The signal was then bandpass filtered at 3 Hz to 10 KHz, and sampled at 20 KHz with 12 bits resolution. The signal was then lowpass filtered at 10 KHz. MUAP waveforms with similar shape were identified and selected from the EMG recording using an unsupervised learning neural network system [4]. Similar MUAPs were averaged to obtain the averaged MUAP waveform, which is thereafter simply referred to as MUAP. The MUAP epoch consisted of 512 samples (25.6 ms). Twenty MUAPs were recorded from each subject.

A total of 800 MUAPs were recorded from 40 subjects, 12 normal (NOR), 13 suffering from myopathy (MYO) and 15 from motor neuron disease (MND). Diagnostic criteria were based on clinical opinion, biochemical data and muscle biopsy. The neural network system was trained and tested for the three classes. Different sets with eight subjects from each group were randomly selected to form the ANN training set, whereas the remaining subjects formed the ANN evaluation set.

3 EMG Feature Extraction

For each subject a matrix of 20 MUAP waveforms x 512 samples, was available for further processing. From each MUAP waveform the following feature sets were extracted:

(i) Time domain parameters

Time domain parameters are the most widely used parameters in clinical neurophysiology for the interpretation of EMG findings. The following time domain parameters were computed from the MUAP waveforms [5]: duration, spike duration, amplitude, area, spike area, number of phases and number of turns.

(ii) Frequency domain parameters

The following frequency domain parameters were computed from the MUAP waveforms: spectral moments of order 0, 1 and 2 (M_0 , M_1 , and M_2), median frequency and quality factor. Spectral moments M_1 and M_2 represent the area of the power spectrum after being weighted by frequency raised to the power of one and two respectively.

(iii) Cepstral coefficients

The cepstral coefficients c_1 to c_{12} were computed from the MUAP signal. The motivation for using the cepstral coefficients is their high discrimination ability documented in speech recognition [6].

(iv) Wavelet coefficients

The wavelet transform (WT) provides a linear two dimensional time-frequency representation and was investigated for describing MUAP morphology. The WT was investigated because it has the ability to localize the changes in the statistics of nonstationary signals and it provides an alternative to the classical Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) which uses a single analysis window [7]. The WT uses short windows at high frequencies and long windows at low frequencies. Three different wavelets were computed: Daubechies 4 (*DAU4***Error! Switch argument not specified.**) with 4 coefficients, Chui (*CH***Error! Switch argument not specified.**) and Battle-Lemarie (*BL***Error! Switch argument not specified.**) [8].

For each subject, the average vector of 20 MUAPs for each feature set was computed which was subsequently used as input to the classifiers.

4 The EMG Decision Support System

In the case of difficult pattern recognition problems, the combination of the outputs of multiple classifiers using for input multiple feature sets extracted from the raw data, can improve the overall classification performance. In the case of noisy or of a limited amount of data, different classifiers often provide different generalisations by realising different decision boundaries. Also, different feature sets provide different representations of the input patterns, containing different classification information. Selecting the best classifier or the best feature set is not necessarily the ideal choice, since potentially valuable information contained in the less successful feature sets or classifiers may not be taken into account. The combination of the results of the different features and the different classifiers increases the probability that the errors of the individual features or classifiers may be compensated by the correct results of the rest [9]. Furthermore according to Perrone [10] the performance of the combiner is never worse than the average of the individual classifiers, but not necessarily better than the best classifier. Also, the error variance of the final result is reduced making the whole system more robust and reliable. The use of a confidence measure by weighting the individual classification results before combining can further improve the overall performance.

In this work, the usefulness of combining neural network classifiers is investigated in the development of a decision support system for the assessment of neuromuscular disorders based on the EMG signal. Six different feature sets were extracted from the MUAP waveforms (as described in section 3) and were inputted into the SOFM classifiers. The

classification results were combined using majority voting and a confidence measure in order to improve the diagnostic yield. Figure 1 illustrates the flowchart of the modular neural network system.

4.1 Self-Organising feature map algorithm

The self-organising feature map (SOFM) algorithm is an unsupervised learning algorithm where the input patterns are freely distributed over the output node matrix [11]. The weights are adapted without supervision in such a way, so that the density distribution of the input data is preserved and represented on the output nodes. This mapping of similar input patterns to output nodes which are close to each other represents a discretisation of the input space, allowing a visualization of the distribution of the input data. The output nodes are usually ordered in a two dimensional grid, and the weights of the output nodes in the neighborhood of the winning output node are adapted simultaneously. The neighborhood around the winning output node, decreases in size over time. The weights of the output nodes in the neighborhood are adapted with

$$w(t+1) = w(t) + \eta h(t) (x - w(t)) \quad (1)$$

where η is the learning rate ($0 < \eta \leq 1$) and $h(t)$ is a decreasing function which decreases with time.

At the end of the training phase, the output nodes were labelled with the class of the majority of the input patterns of the training set, assigned to each node. In the evaluation phase, an input pattern was assigned to the output node with the weight vector closest to the input vector, and it was said to belong to the class label of the winning output node where it had been assigned.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of the modular neural network with a confidence measure which decides the contribution of each feature set to the final classification result.

4.2 Combining classifiers with a confidence measure

In order to enhance the classification success rate, a multi-feature modular neural network system based on SOFM classifiers is used. Beyond the classification result, the classifiers yield a confidence measure on how reliable the classification result is. The classification results are combined and the confidence measure decides the contribution of each feature set to the final result. The idea is that some feature sets may be more successful for specific regions of the input population. The confidence measure is calculated based on the number of input patterns assigned per class to the

nearest neighbors on the self-organizing map during the training phase. For this purpose the eight output nodes of the neighborhood of the winning node are considered. If (0,0) are the indices of the winning output node, the confidence measure is calculated as follows:

$$Cf_k = n_k(0,0) + [n_k(-1,-1)+n_k(-1,1)+n_k(1,-1)+n_k(1,1)] 0.5 + [n_k(-1,0)+n_k(0,-1)+n_k(0,1)+n_k(1,0)] 0.3536 \quad (2)$$

where $k=\{1, 2, 3\}$ indicates the class, and $n_k(i,j)$ is the number of input patterns of the class k assigned to output node (i,j) during the training phase. The neighbor nodes perpendicular to the winning node are given values 0.5 whereas the diagonally located nodes values 0.3536. During the evaluation phase an input pattern is assigned to the winning output node and the percentage confidence measure is calculated as

$$Cp_m = Cf_m / (Cf_1 + Cf_2 + Cf_3) \quad (3)$$

where m is the winning class where the evaluation input pattern has been assigned. Cp_m is the output of the SOFM classifier which indicates that the specific input pattern has been assigned to class m with a percentage confidence measure value Cp_m . The outputs of the N different classifiers for the same winning class m are added and the total values SCp_m are calculated for all classes

$$SCp_m = \sum_{l=1}^N Cp_{ml} \quad (4)$$

where $m=\{1, 2, 3\}$. The final classification result is the class with the maximum value

$$SCp_{max} = \max \{ SCp_1, SCp_2, SCp_3 \} .$$

In the same way as in Eq. 3 the final percentage confidence measure can be calculated as

$$FCp = SCp_{max} / (SCp_1 + SCp_2 + SCp_3) . \quad (5)$$

Values of FCp close to unity indicate a high degree of confidence about the correctness of the classification result whereas values close to 0.33 indicate a low degree of confidence.

5 Results

A total of 24 subjects, 8 NOR, 8 MYO and 8 MND, were used for training the SOFM classifiers, whereas a total of 16 subjects, 4 NOR, 5 MYO and 7 MND were used for evaluation. Due to the rather limited amount of the input data and in order to verify the correctness of the classification results a bootstrapping procedure was used. The system was trained and evaluated using ten different bootstrap sets where in each set 24 different subjects were selected at random for training and 16 different subjects for evaluation. The mean percentage and the standard deviation (Std) of the correct classifications score, i.e. diagnostic yield, for the ten bootstrap evaluation sets was computed for the six different feature sets. Table I tabulates the mean and standard deviation of the diagnostic yield of the neural network

Table I Mean and standard deviation of the diagnostic yield for the evaluation set of the neural network EMG diagnostic system, after bootstrapping the available data for ten different sets of subjects. The diagnostic yield is given for the six feature sets, their average, their combining with simple majority voting, and their combining with confidence measure.

<i>Feature set</i>	<i>Feature set vector size</i>	<i>Diagnostic yield %</i>
Time domain parameters	7	79.2 ± 11.2
Frequency domain parameters	5	70.6 ± 14.9
Cepstral coefficients	12	67.3 ± 10.3
Wavelet transform DAU4	16	72.7 ± 9.2
Wavelet transform CH	16	58.8 ± 11.0
Wavelet transform BL	16	66.2 ± 8.9
Average :		69.1 ± 11.0
Combining with simple majority voting :		76.9 ± 7.5
Combining with confidence measure :		79.6 ± 6.9

Table II Mean and standard deviation of the final confidence measure percentage for the three disease classes.

<i>Confidence measure %</i>			
<i>NOR</i>	<i>MYO</i>	<i>MND</i>	<i>Average</i>
77.0 ± 9.7	89.4 ± 4.8	83.5 ± 8.4	83.8 ± 4.5

EMG diagnostic system. The best diagnostic yield was achieved when the time domain parameters were used as input into the SOFM classifier and it was 79.2%. The better results obtained by the time domain parameters can be justified by the relative simple shape of the EMG signal at low to moderate force levels. The average diagnostic yield for the individual feature sets was 69.1% whereas when combining the six classification results with simple majority voting was 76.9%. The use of the confidence measure enhanced further the diagnostic yield to 79.6%. Also the diagnostic yield variance was reduced. Table II tabulates the mean and standard deviation of the final percentage confidence measure FCp for the three classes. The higher confidence measure is 89.4% for the MYO group where the lower for the

NOR group with 77.0%. The lower confidence measure for the NOR group can be attributed to the fact that the characteristics of the normal group are located in between of the characteristics of the two pathogenic groups.

The classifiers were implemented using the SOFM algorithm as it was given in the MATLAB neural networks toolbox [12]. The SOFM algorithm was trained for 3000 learning epochs and the 24 subjects of the training set were distributed over a 6 x 6 output node matrix.

6 Concluding remarks

This study shows that combining neural network classifiers trained with multiple feature sets can be used successfully in EMG decision making. Because of the overlap among the three classes of the different MUAP features, the unsupervised learning SOFM algorithm was used which resulted in an efficient mapping of the MUAP data. Furthermore, based on the number of input patterns assigned per class to the nearest neighbors on the self-organizing map during the training phase, a confidence measure was extracted and used for weighting the classification results. The use of the confidence measure enhanced further the overall classification performance.

In conclusion, the results in this work show that neural networks are a promising tool in solving difficult pattern recognition problems. The combining of multiple neural classifiers in conjunction with the use of a confidence measure for weighting the classification results can significantly improve the overall classification performance. The diagnostic results could be verified further using more data from more subjects, both for training and evaluating the system. In addition, other forms of data like muscle biopsy, biochemical and molecular genetic findings, and clinical data may be combined into a hybrid diagnostic system for neuromuscular diseases.

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